

Risks and Challenges associated with the chain of custody of cryptographic assets in law enforcement operations.

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Abstract—The emergence of cryptocurrencies represents a radical change in the transmission of value in a disintermediated manner, which in many cases means that they are beyond the control of regulators and law enforcement bodies. This circumstance, together with the growing training in the use of crypto-asset management resources, has led to an increase in their popularity, and it is becoming increasingly common to find these crypto-assets in criminal operations. From a law enforcement point of view, the use of crypto-currency poses a challenge in terms of the procedure for investigating crimes involving the ancillary or principal use of crypto-assets. Indeed, in addition to the problem of tracking and attribution, there is the complex issue of interception, custody and, if the investigation concludes that there is no criminal activity, the return of the cryptographic asset to its owner. This paper analyses the challenges facing law enforcement investigation of criminal events involving cryptocurrencies that may have been intercepted. In particular, it addresses the difficulties in achieving adequate protection of the chain of custody of crypto-assets, all in accordance with the inalienable criterion of the presumption of innocence that must govern all criminal proceedings.

Index Terms—Cryptocurrencies, Law Enforcement Custody, Cybersecurity, Digital Assets

Type of contribution: *Research in process*

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the emergence of the first cryptocurrencies in 2009 and due to their increasing popularity, resulting from the ease of protection against traceability by regulators and law enforcement bodies, it is becoming increasingly common in law enforcement operations to obtain technological evidence related to this crypto asset. Because of its innovative nature and complex technology, ensuring its preservation throughout the police investigation and the entire criminal process makes this task challenging.

In every criminal process, there exists the so-called principle of innocence, a fundamental pillar in the legal system of many countries. This principle establishes that a person must be considered innocent until proven otherwise through valid evidence in a fair trial. This principle is based on the fundamental right to ensure the presumption of innocence, whereby a person cannot be treated or considered guilty of a crime unless their guilt is proven beyond a reasonable doubt.

In every law enforcement operation preceding the criminal process, there exists an investigation and collection of evidences linked to the criminal act; those evidences, in the phase of oral trial, will constitute material proof of the

facts to be demonstrated. It is here where the custody of such evidence takes on special relevance, due to the need of ensuring that they have been handled carefully, preserved, unaltered, and intact, from the moment they were recovered until they are included as evidence at the Court, so that means that the chain of custody must be guaranteed. Therefore, the custody of digital evidences entails the deployment of technical measures. [1], [2] to ensuring the probated nature of the evidence and its legal validity.

In order to support the process of acquiring and preserving digital evidence, in 2013, the UNE 71506/2013 standard was developed. [3] which defines the forensic analysis process within the electronic evidence management cycle. This process is composed of several phases:

- **Preservation:** the aim of this phase is to maintain the validity and reliability of the original evidences at all times, ensuring that the experts performing these tasks have adequate means to avoid external interference and to ensure that the evidences are stored securely until the end of the expert process.
- **Acquisition:** this phase covers the aspects related to the acquisition of evidence, with special mention of the state of the systems, given that the acquisition process will not be the same whether the systems are on or off, and that any action could compromise the integrity of the evidence.
- **Documentation:** The aim of this phase is to document the entire procedure, from the start of the analysis until the expert report is sent to the applicant. All processes carried out and tools used shall be documented, following a defined time sequence. It is important to note that the chain of custody shall reflect all the steps carried out during the handling of the evidence.
- **Analyses:** During this phase, a series of processes and tasks will be carried out in an attempt to provide answers to questions related to the event that motivated the research.
- **Presentation:** This is the last phase of the process and is where the expert report is drawn up with all the information obtained throughout the analysis process. This report will be sent together with the evidence control document to provide transparency and greater traceability to the process.

When dealing with cryptographic assets, this process becomes more complex, even when it is possible to overcome the barrier of being able to intercept the crypto-assets, after having had access to the private keys of the cryptographic wallet involved in the criminal act, the challenge of secure custody arises. This is difficult to achieve because there are currently no totally secure and reliable solutions that allow for this due to the challenges they pose, including their technology, their decentralised nature, and the lack of regulation in many countries.

To define what a crypto-asset is, reference should be made to Article 3 of the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on crypto-asset markets. [4], and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937, which defines the cryptoasset as follows: "digital representation of value or rights that can be transferred and stored electronically, using decentralised recording technology or similar technology". [5].

It should be noted that the decentralised nature of cryptocurrencies is based on the fact that there is no central governing entity, so these digital assets are neither issued nor controlled by a central authority. Cryptocurrencies operate using distributed technology, and although cryptocurrencies such as IOTA use a technology called Tangle, where each transaction is directly linked to multiple previous transactions represented by a directed acyclic graph (DAG), most of them make use of the blockchain, where various computers connected to a decentralized network review, record, and validate all transactions securely, ensuring the immutability of the blocks, and transparent, because all data that are stored in a blockchain are visible to all participants in the network. It should be noted that for this paper, we will focus on blockchain technology. An interesting aspect to highlight is that although the Tangle network is a public access technology, when talking about the blockchain technology we can differentiate between public blockchain and private blockchain, although most of the most used and popular cryptocurrencies are based on public blockchain. This is important because being public, anyone can access the record of transactions and in the case of blockchain, anyone can propose himself as a validator and recorder of new transactions following protocols of coordination of writing processes such as the so-called proof of work (PoW). [6], as well as various mechanisms for monitoring and controlling access to information on a blockchain. [7].

Although there is currently no global legislation on cryptoassets, many countries are strengthening their regulatory frameworks to specifically address the use of cryptocurrencies in illicit activities with the intention of protecting users. In Europe, can be found the European regulation on crypto-asset markets (MiCA - Markets in Crypto Assets [8]) to regulate the issuance and provision of services related to cryptoassets, i.e. currencies whose volatility is controlled by some form of collateral value (either fiat currency or other collateral such as gold) or by algorithmic supervision. The regulation was ratified by the European Parliament on 20 April 2023, the first framework of its kind in the world, providing clear guidelines and rules for cryptomarket participants to ensure consumer protection and maintain market integrity. The regulation includes issuers and service providers, with

the aim of protecting consumers and investors, as well as increasing financial stability and innovation. The law will be implemented between mid-2024 and early 2025 and positions Europe as an attractive region in this market.

Regulation (EU) 2015/847 of the European Parliament and of the Council, known as the TFR regulation, aims primarily to address the risks associated with money laundering, terrorist financing and organised crime in the context of money transfers. As with FIAT money, the TFR regulation aims to ensure that all transactions involving crypto-assets are traceable and that the persons transferring and receiving the money can be fully identified, where at least one of the service providers involved in the transfer is established in the European Union. [9].

As an additional measure, it is worth noting the recent regulatory change agreed by the European Parliament on 22 March 2024, where all transactions through self-custodied wallets have been banned.[10].

It is increasingly common for companies operating in the cryptocurrency space to be subject to these regulations and to comply with KYC (Know Your Customer), AML (Anti-Money Laundering) and CFT (Countering the Financing of Terrorism) requirements in order to operate legally and avoid sanctions.

- **KYC:** It is a process that requires financial institutions and other entities to verify the identity of their customers by collecting information on identity and financial activity, such as name, address, date of birth, identification number, among others. The objective of this process is to prevent money laundering and other illicit activities[11].

- **AML:** It refers to policies, laws and procedures designed to prevent the conversion of money obtained from illegal activities into legal money. In the context of cryptocurrencies, AML regulations generally require exchanges to implement controls to detect and prevent money laundering by conducting due diligence and reporting suspicious transactions to financial authorities [12].

- **CFT:** In the field of cryptocurrencies, CFT regulations often go hand in hand with AML measures and focus on preventing the use of funds to finance terrorist activities. CFT regulations require financial institutions and other market actors to implement controls to identify and report suspicious financial activities that could be related to terrorist financing.

Also noteworthy is the **Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA)** [13], which creates a binding and comprehensive framework for the management of information and communication technology risks in the financial sector in the European Union. This regulation lays down the technical standards that financial institutions and their technology service providers must implement in their ICT systems, as well as the **Pilot scheme regulation DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology)** [14] which is the first of the rules foreseen under the EU's digital finance package.

Although every day, the legislative framework to regulate the "crypto world" is getting stronger and stronger, with new standards such as ISO 20022 (a global messaging standard developed to provide a consistent framework for the electronic exchange of data between financial institutions) and ISO 20022 (a global messaging standard developed to provide a consistent framework for the electronic exchange of data

between financial institutions) are being implemented[15]) and it can be observed that certain cryptocurrencies such as RP, HBAR, XLM, ADA, ALGO, IOTA and QNT comply with these standards, it is true that due to the complex technology that supports them, risks associated with the custody of cryptocurrencies can be found, facts that will make the process of reliably guaranteeing this process challenging.

II. GENERAL RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH THE SAFEKEEPING OF CRYPTO-ASSETS

The custody of cryptoassets comprises the entire set of actions aimed at keeping cryptographic assets secure and protected against loss, theft or unauthorised access.

The biggest challenge arises from the underlying distributed technology, where unlike traditional financial institutions, where assets are physically present or stored in centralised databases, cryptocurrencies are stored on the blockchain.

The crypto wallet, known as a "wallet" or cryptocurrency purse, allows users to store, send and receive crypto assets. It works similarly to a physical wallet, but instead of containing fiat money, it contains cryptographic keys, or "keys", which represent ownership of cryptocurrencies and their addresses, and interacts with the blockchain to create and sign transactions.

Cryptographic wallets are based on the concepts of asymmetric cryptography where a user obtains a pair of cryptographic keys (public key and private key) and uses them to perform different actions.

Public Key is similar to a bank account number and can be given to anyone to make a money transfer, without the risk of them being able to withdraw the funds stored there. The public key generates addresses for receiving, querying and viewing the status of funds.

Private Key is the one that 'protects' the cryptoassets. It is the key that gives access to the funds stored in the safe, which in the case of cryptocurrencies is known as a wallet. It is the most important element and must be kept without making it public because whoever has the private key will have access to the wallet and will be able to carry out transactions. An analogy could be made between the private key and the bank card PIN.

Sending a transaction using cryptoassets can be compared to sending an encrypted message combined with a digital signature. When Alice wants to send an encrypted message to Bob, Alice encrypts the message with Bob's public key. Subsequently, Bob would use his own private key to decrypt the message and gain access to the information. To make a digital signature, Alice must use her own private key to do so.

For crypto-asset transactions, Alice will send the transaction to Bob's wallet identified by Bob's public key. Subsequently, Bob will have to use his private key to access his wallet. It should be noted that although Alice has sent the transaction to Bob's wallet, Alice has had to make use of her own private key in order to access the source wallet and authorise the transfer.

Based on the above information, the following is an overview of the different daily actions with wallets and the keys, public or private, that can be performed:

- **Wallet Creation:** When a new wallet is created, a pair of cryptographic keys are generated: a public key and a private key. The public key is a unique wallet address used to receive funds, while the private key is a secret password used to sign and authorise transactions. It should be noted that the same private key could be used to control and manage multiple cryptographic wallet addresses (multiple public addresses). This would be especially useful in case a user wants to have different public addresses for different purposes, e.g. use some of them for daily transactions and use others for long-term savings.
- **Wallet Access:** To access the cryptographic wallet and carry out transactions, it is necessary to provide the private key, although it is true that if we have delegated the custody of the cryptoassets to an Exchange, it will be the Exchange that will be the custodian of this key and in our case we will only have to use our username and password to be able to access our wallet.[16]
- **Get Payments:** To receive funds in the crypto wallet, it is the public key that plays a crucial role. Through this key, a third party could send funds.
- **Send Payments:** To send funds from the crypto wallet, the public address of the recipient and the private key of the originating wallet are needed to sign and authorise the transaction. Once the transaction is sent, it is transmitted to the corresponding blockchain for processing and confirmation.
- **Registration on the blockchain:** All cryptocurrency transactions are permanently recorded on the blockchain, creating a decentralised public record that provides transparency and security for cryptocurrency transactions.
Before defining in depth possible risks associated with the custody of cryptoassets, it is necessary to analyse the different types of wallets that can be used.
As a general classification, the different types of wallets can be divided into hot wallets or cold wallets.
- **Hot Wallets:** This type of wallet is constantly connected to the internet and is always online. It is often the most common wallet model used by exchanges to store funds and is a popular choice for users because of its ease of use (users do not need to manually sign each transaction), its simple and user-friendly interface, and because it allows access from different types of devices (desktops, laptops, tablets, smartphones).
- **Cold Wallets:** This type of wallet allows keys to be stored without being connected to the internet and the only time it is necessary to connect the cold wallet to the internet is when you want to sign the transaction, so this connection is ephemeral. They are the most secure type of wallet and although the risk of a cyber-attack is significantly lower compared to hot wallets, there are several attack vectors, such as social engineering attacks[17] or physical attacks, which could compromise such wallets. Among the existing types of cold wallets we can find:
 - **Hardware Wallets:** are very easy to use physical devices that are usually in the form of a portable hard disk or USB memory stick. One of their many

features is the ability to add an additional PIN or password so that if they are lost, they cannot be used by third parties.

- **Paper Wallets:** contain the address of the wallet and a private key. This private key will be necessary to access the cryptoassets. This type of wallet is very useful for storing and safeguarding funds if the intention is not to move or use them for a long period of time.

Another important aspect to consider is that in order to ensure effective security of crypto-assets, it is necessary to understand and apply the fundamental principles of the **CID** triad [18](a model designed to guide information security policies within an organisation, being the fundamental pillars for data protection).

- **Confidentiality (C):** refers to the protection of information against unauthorised access. The aim is to protect information so that only authorised persons can access it.
- **Integrity (I):** refers to the protection of information. It involves ensuring that data is not altered in an unauthorised manner, guaranteeing its accuracy and trustworthiness.
- **Availability (D):** refers to the ability to access data when needed, ensuring reliable access to information by authorised persons.

Based on the above information, it should be noted that all the risks associated with the custody of crypto-assets are based on confidentiality, as it is the **secure storage of the private key** the fundamental pillar in the custody of cryptoassets, since possession of this key guarantees access to the funds. It should not be forgotten that, as it is a decentralised technology, **anyone, anywhere in the world with access to the private key**, would be able to transact with the cryptoassets stored in the wallet.

Of the different wallets on the market, the most vulnerable to security threats (cyber-attacks, identity theft) are the following **hot wallets**, due to being constantly connected to the internet.

As previously stated, hot wallets are the wallets most commonly used by exchanges, although nowadays most exchanges make a combined use of different types of wallets. An important aspect, which is often misunderstood by users, is that when using an exchange to trade cryptoassets, the user only has a username and password to connect to the service, but the user only has a username and password to log in to the exchange. **it is the exchange itself that is the owner and custodian of the private keys.** Therefore, if through a cyberattack, a cybercriminal were to get hold of any access credentials to the exchange, or what could be worse, if he were to get hold of any credentials with administrator permissions on that platform, that cybercriminal could transfer the cryptoassets to other wallets leaving the users of the exchange, the "supposed" owners of the crypto wallets, without access and without funds.[19]

As an alternative and aiming at the safe custody of crypto-assets, one could think about **cold wallets** due to their technical characteristics and their functionality of being able to store the keys without being connected to the internet,

but here again, problems related to one of the pillars of the information security triad such as integrity or availability as well as other potential problems could arise[20].

In addition, when using or wanting to use cold wallets, the user may face some risks associated with cold wallets, which are listed below:

- 1) **Initial cost:** Cold wallets (hardware) have a higher initial cost compared to other types of wallets. This can be a barrier for some users.
- 2) **Ease of use for beginners:** Some cold wallets may have a steeper learning curve, which can make them difficult to use for those new to cryptocurrencies.
- 3) **Possibility of physical loss or damage:** As physical devices, cold wallets are subject to risk of loss or damage. If the device is lost or damaged, this could result in permanent loss of access to the funds stored in the wallet.
- 4) **Security updates:** Although cold wallets are generally secure, it is important to be aware of security updates. If they are not updated regularly, they could become vulnerable to new threats.
- 5) **Limited compatibility:** Some cold wallets may have limitations on the number and variety of cryptocurrencies they support. It is crucial to make sure that your chosen cold wallet is compatible with the cryptocurrencies you plan to store.
- 6) **Periodic disconnection:** If a cold wallet is not periodically connected to the internet, it could become obsolete and lose the ability to verify new transactions or updates to the blockchain network.

Another aspect to consider is the risk caused by cyber-attacks or malware installed on devices that will make use of crypto-asset wallets. [16] [21]. One category of malicious tools that have become very popular in the crypto-asset arena are so-called cryptocurrency wallet drainers or "crypto drainers". [22]. Este malware first appeared in the year 2023. They are designed to (quickly) empty cryptocurrency wallets automatically by extracting all or only the most valuable assets contained in them, and inserting them into the wallets of the drainer's operators [23].

Finally, another fact that should not be forgotten is that, although the probability of obtaining the private key from a public key is extremely low and it could be said that with current technology this is computationally improbable, as there is a probability greater than zero, there is a minimal possibility of compromising any type of cryptographic wallet, so chance should not be ruled out.

III. RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH THE LAW ENFORCEMENT CUSTODY OF CRYPTO-ASSETS

When analysing the risks associated with crypto-asset safekeeping, it can be seen that the factors are the same as those affecting any individual user, however, what must be highlighted as different is the impact and therefore the risks and consequences that can arise following the ineffective safekeeping or loss of crypto-assets.

In the previous section, we have defined different risks that may arise when it comes to the safe custody of cryptocurrencies and while it is true that for a private user the greatest risk

is the loss of stored funds due to circumstances such as the loss of private keys, data integrity to access the paper wallet, availability in hardware wallets and loss of the recovery seed phrase, hacks, etc., when analysing police custody, the impact is much greater because in police/criminal operations fundamental rights are at stake, such as the right to liberty and security of those involved such as the right to freedom of movement. ..., when looking at police custody, the impact is much greater due to the fact that in police/criminal operations fundamental rights of those involved such as the right to liberty and security are at stake [24] and rights to presumption of innocence and fair trial [25], It is therefore necessary to rule out the possibility that the lack of administrative or judicial control over the pieces of conviction of the crime, thus avoiding the possibility of generating an error on any decisive data for the judgment of criminality [26].

That is why the **chain of custody**, is of vital importance in the course of a criminal investigation in order to ensure the authenticity, unalterability and indemnity of sources of evidence. While it is true that through blockchain technology one could check the status/balance of a wallet at a given date, what cannot be guaranteed is that there are no further movements and the cryptoasset changes hands, because the blockchain as a whole cannot be seized, and that is why the chain of custody should focus on the safe custody of the cryptographic keys stored in the wallets.

As indicated above, a determining factor that considerably increases the difficulty in the custody of cryptocurrencies is their decentralised technology nature, and unlike what could happen with the custody of a physical device/item stored in a specific location, where access to it would have to overcome different physical controls, or what could happen with access to FIAT money stored in bank accounts and protected by a central entity, to access the content of virtual wallets, one only has to have access to the private key of the wallet, being able to access these wallets from anywhere in the world.

In the following, different scenarios will be defined to highlight the importance of secure crypto-asset custody in law enforcement operations and the impact caused by the lack of technical solutions on this aspect:

What would happen if crypto-assets used as evidence in criminal proceedings were to disappear at some point in time?

If crypto-assets used as evidence were to disappear during criminal proceedings, the consequences would be similar to the disappearance of any other evidentiary evidence, and could have various effects, depending on the importance of the evidence and the specific circumstances of the case. Some of the consequences could be:

- 1) **Difficulty in proving the fact:** If the compromised evidence is crucial to the prosecution or defence, its disappearance may hinder a party's ability to prove the fact itself.
- 2) **Suspicious of tampering or breach of the chain of custody:** Such suspicions due to tampering, misconduct or negligence on the part of the custodial authorities could lead to internal investigations and call into question the integrity of the entire criminal process.
- 3) **Possibility to request the exclusion of evidence:** The

party affected by the disappearance of the evidence could request the exclusion of other related evidence, arguing that the chain of custody or the integrity of the proceedings has been compromised.

- 4) **Potential impact on sentencing:** Depending on the importance of the missing evidence and how it affects the case, its absence could influence the court's final decision and ultimately the sentence handed down.

What would happen if there was a leak of the private key of the wallet used to store cryptocurrencies seized in a criminal operation?

Due to the lack of reliable technology, certain processes in police records linked to the seizure of crypto-assets must be carried out manually involving different actors. In order to proceed with the seizure of cryptocurrencies, a cold wallet must be created, which will be the receiving wallet for the seized cryptoassets and which will safeguard and preserve the digital assets throughout the criminal proceedings.

At this point, a possible risk could arise because, although it is not the norm among the different actors in charge of enforcing the legal system, it could be the case that one of them could succumb to the temptation of appropriating the cryptoassets by having access to the private key at a given moment because the protocols/procedures for carrying out the intervention are not entirely secure in this respect. This would not be something new and, although they are usually isolated events, there have already been cases in other areas such as those related to drug trafficking where some evidence has been compromised due to the improper performance, poor morality and lack of integrity of those involved in the process. This is why, within the different organisations, there are internal affairs units that investigate this type of actions.

If for any reason, whether human or technical, the private key of the new wallet were to be compromised, we would have the same potential risk addressed in the previous point.

What would happen if a defendant in a criminal investigation who had cryptocurrencies seized from him is finally acquitted?

The procedure for returning seized cryptoassets to an acquitted defendant is similar to the procedure for returning other types of property. While it is true that this procedure may vary depending on jurisdiction and local laws, a number of risks and challenges may arise when dealing with the return of forfeited cryptoassets due to the unique nature of these digital currencies.

While other risks could be discussed, some specific risks impacting the custody of digital assets will be discussed below:

- **Security of private keys:** The security of the private keys controlling the crypto-assets is critical to prevent unauthorised access to the funds. During the confiscation and safekeeping process, it is crucial to maintain the security of these keys to prevent theft or loss of the cryptoassets. If during the process a third party were to gain access to the funds stored in the digital wallets and transfer the assets held in them, we would find ourselves in a situation where it would be impossible to replace the assets seized from the defendants in the criminal proceedings in the event of a finding of not guilty.

- **Risk of irreversible loss:** If private keys are lost or damaged in any way during the escrow process, the crypto-assets associated with those keys could be irreversibly lost. This could result in the total loss of the funds, which would be impossible to recover, representing a significant risk for the defendant. As in the previous case, in this situation, it would be impossible to replace the assets seized during the criminal proceedings.

Given the complexity and risks associated with the return of confiscated cryptoassets, one could consider the alternative solution of converting them into FIAT currency and carrying out traditional custody of this currency, but here again there are other risks, such as market volatility, which could impact the value recovered by the defendant:

- Because of the extremely volatile nature of crypto-assets [27], which can undergo significant changes in a short period of time impacting the value of seized digital assets, fluctuating considerably during the time they are in the custody of the authorities, the defendant may recover less than he originally had if the value decreases.

It is for all these reasons that a solution must be sought that allows the custody of the asset itself, and due to the fact that the blockchain as a whole cannot be requisitioned, we must focus on maintaining the confidentiality of the private key that allows access to the cryptoasset, guaranteeing that it can be accessed to carry out the necessary operations at any given time.

IV. CHALLENGES

While it is true that any country with basic asset recovery/seizure legislation could apply such legislation to crypto-assets, a number of technical challenges and procedural challenges have to be taken into account when developing an appropriate solution for the safe custody of cryptocurrencies, which are described below:

A. TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

As indicated above, the biggest problem we face when it comes to securely guarding cryptographic assets in law enforcement operations is the impossibility of seizing the blockchain as a whole, so all efforts must be focused on guaranteeing the confidentiality of the private key that protects access to cryptographic wallets.

Nowadays it is difficult to have **solutions directly implementing advanced cryptography** [28]. When talking about privacy, we must think about confidentiality, and we must focus on cryptographic solutions that enable trading at different levels of trust. The chain of custody of cryptoassets requires different trading modalities, so there is some equivalence between the needs for privacy protection and the requirements for trust trading in custody of highly sensitive assets. In fact, zero-trust, data minimisation and selective disclosure of attributes solutions could be applied to both paradigms.

A technical solution must be found to prevent unwanted access to the assets under custody, which is complex because due to the decentralised nature of the technology behind cryptocurrencies, anyone, anywhere in the world with access to the private keys could make use of the digital assets stored in a wallet. One could think of isolating the technical

solution only to cold wallets, but apart from the previously mentioned problems, one would have to look for a place to store such wallets securely, and as a consequence, new risks associated with their custody could appear, especially those related to integrity. What would happen if liquid spilled on a paper wallet and compromised the information written on it? What would happen in case of a physical disaster at the wallet storage place? What would happen if a hardware wallet stopped working? It is true that many manufacturers of such devices offer the option of restoration through seed phrases (a master key that can regenerate all the private keys of a hardware wallet and is composed of a set of words, usually between 12 or 24 words [29].) but this would impact on the need for secure custody of hardware wallets and recovery phrases.

[Comments JMA aqui](#): A technical solution could be to split the private key into n-subkeys, but this solution would not prevent the private key from being compromised. While it is true that an attacker would have to get hold of the different fragments to compose the private key to operate with the cryptoassets, this solution would not guarantee total security and would not prevent the private key from being discovered by chance.

As an evolution of the previous solution, one could think of multi-signature wallets, where each transaction requires multiple keys to authorise them. While it is true that this solution would improve security, it also has several potential problems associated with it:

- Complexity in setting up and managing the wallet, requiring more technical knowledge.
- Risk of key loss: by requiring multiple private keys to authorise a transaction, there is an increased risk of losing one of the keys.
- Coordination: in order to perform a transaction, it is necessary to coordinate this action among all key holders.
- Transaction add-on costs[30].

As a final objective, a technical solution must be sought that guarantees the confidentiality, availability and integrity of cryptographic assets.

B. PROCEDURAL CHALLENGES

Procedural challenges refer to any obstacle or difficulty related to the procedures, processes or methods used to carry out a specific task or achieve a given objective and our case study, the implementation of a tool for the secure custody of cryptoassets in the chain of custody, has some of the following:

- Lack of clear protocols for identity and access management, which would make it difficult to properly assign roles and permissions to protect cryptographic assets.
- Custodial security issues, which could cause cryptographic assets stored in a crypto wallet to disappear.
- Lack of established audit and compliance procedures, which would make it difficult to ensure transparency and compliance with relevant regulations.
- Training and education of staff, which could result in operational errors or misunderstandings, affecting the security and integrity of digital assets. This could be due

Fig. 1. Figure 1. Chain of custody flow chart

to the failure to provide adequate training to staff on crypto-asset safekeeping procedures and policies.

- Governance in digital systems, in a broad sense, requires an effective and efficient combination of technological solutions and legal and regulatory requirements, all of which must be in line with the specifics of the scope of application. In other words, the implementation of a BLT (Business, Legal, Technological) framework must also be on the horizon in the field of cryptoeconomics.[31].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the safe custody of cryptocurrencies is a fundamental pillar in criminal operations where cryptographic assets have been intervened, a fact that is constantly growing not only in Spain but also worldwide.

Ensuring the security and protection of these assets requires a holistic approach that addresses technical and procedural challenges ranging from the implementation of robust security measures to compliance with specific regulations where trust and integrity must be prioritised in every part of the process. It should be noted that the secure custody of cryptocurrencies continues to evolve, driven by the advancement of technology and an increased awareness of the associated risks.

Although there are currently several solutions on the market that could help to improve aspects of providing more secure custody of cryptoassets, such as the use of cold wallets, whose method of use has been called into question following the latest regulatory agreement on self-custodied wallets, the use of cold wallets has been called into question following the latest agreement on self-custodied wallets.[32], or make use

of multi-signature wallets, **there is no standard technical solution that is easy to implement, neither for developers nor for end-users.**

While the challenges around safe custody of cryptocurrencies are significant, there are also opportunities for innovation and collaboration. The development of advanced technological solutions, such as multi-sig custody that distributes control of funds among multiple authorised parties, thus mitigating the risk of a single point of failure, asset tokenisation that offers the possibility to represent traditional assets in the form of digital tokens, enabling more efficient and transparent management of assets in blockchain environments, and key management platforms that provide a secure means of storing and managing the private keys associated with cryptoasset addresses, thus providing an additional layer of protection against malicious attacks and loss of funds, promise to strengthen security and trust in the cryptocurrency ecosystem.

What is to be achieved is a robust and functional solution that allows users to make use of it without having to possess high technical knowledge, providing them with the confidence and security necessary to ensure the safekeeping of crypto assets.

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